

The Role of Low-Emission Hydrogen in Developing Countries: A Techno-Economic Assessment of Hydrogen Pathways in Colombia

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APPENDIX A. Calibration results

The calibration year was 2021. We conducted a comparison between the model results and the end-use energy reported by the Colombian energy balance in 2021 [1], which yielded an acceptable error of -1.7%, as illustrated in Figure A1. In terms of energy production, the fitting was also reasonably accurate, with a relative error of 1%, as indicated in Figure A2. The differences observed are primarily due to the variations in bioethanol-gasoline and biodiesel-diesel blending, as the model assumes a constant blending percentage (8% for bioethanol and 10% for biodiesel), whereas the country has varying percentages based on the region. We also compared the results of GHG emissions. The model's outcome was 82.6 MtCO_{2e}, while the reference value was 85 MtCO_{2e} [2], resulting in a relative error of -2.8%.

Figure A1. Model results versus real end-use energy in 2021.

Figure A2. Model results versus real produced energy in 2021.

APPENDIX B. Additional results

Figure B1. Water demand for electrolysis by scenario.

Figure B2. Evolution of installed capacities in dedicated units for electrolysis by scenario

Figure B3. Evolution of installed capacity in the power sector by scenario.

Acknowledgment

This material has been produced under the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme, which brings together leading research organizations and is led out of the STEER centre, Loughborough University. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies. This work was developed with the Energy Transition Council (ETC), which assisted in identifying needed research areas and connected to relevant stakeholders for a discussion on essential aspects of research.

References

- [1] UPME. Balance Energético Colombiano 2021. 2022.
- [2] OLADE. Panorama Energético de América Latina y el Caribe 2022. 2022.